

Manufacturing of CF/PEEK Thermoplastic Composites From Flexible Preforms

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ABSTRACT

Commingled yarn and powder/sheath fibre bundle are two flexible thermoplastic composite preforms, consisting of a blended combination of reinforcing fibre yarn (e.g. carbon fibres) and a yarn spun from a thermoplastic resin or polymer resin powder. These preforms can be used as the basic filament yarns to be interwoven, braided or knitted to produce textile preforms for two- or three-dimensional composite parts. When heat and pressure are then applied, the thermoplastic yarn and powder/sheath melt, thus wetting the reinforcing fibres and forming an amorphous thermoplastic resin binder. In the subsequent cooling step, the system is transferred into a rigid composite material. In this paper, investigation on fundamental mechanisms which govern impregnation process, consolidation quality and the resulting mechanical properties of CF/PEEK commingled yarn and powder/sheath fibre bundle composites are highlighted, compared with those of APC-2 CF/PEEK composite.

INTRODUCTION

The argument for the advantages of thermoplastic composites lies on their potential for rapid, low-cost mass production. During the last decade, great efforts have been made to produce innovative/cost-effective preforms for manufacturing fibre-reinforced thermoplastic composites. Commingled/hybrid yarns and powder/sheath fibre bundle and fabrics, representing some kind of a "dry impregnation", have been developed and technologically demonstrated for various applications [1]. In both cases, fibre yarn/bundle consists of a blended combination of reinforcing fibres and thermoplastic filaments or powder from the bulk polymer matrix. In the commingled state, the multi-filament fibres are scattered amongst one another at the filament level, while in powder/sheath fibre bundles, the individual rovings of reinforcing fibres were mingled with very fine thermoplastic matrix powder and then bound together by a thin jacket (sheath) of the same polymer matrix. Both prepreg forms retain the high flexibility such that when a fabric is woven from these materials, the fabric can be designed to be highly conformable and drapeable. The present study is intended to provide a deeper insight into the impregnation and consolidation behaviour of these flexible preforms. Impregnation mechanisms and consolidation quality of

unidirectional CF/PEEK composites were investigated using a small compression mould with a laboratory hot press at different processing conditions (i.e. applied pressure, holding time and processing temperature). Based on investigations on impregnation mechanisms, impregnation models for qualitatively describing the consolidation processes of were developed. The models predict the variations of void content during consolidation as well as the time and pressure required to reach full consolidation.

MATERIALS AND PROCESSING

The CF/PEEK commingled yarn supplied by BASF, Germany, which consists of a 60:40 wt-% mixture of carbon (AS4, Hercules) and PEEK fibres (150G, 25-40 mm in diameter). The "as-received" commingled yarn was prepared by a proper "sizing" to prevent the unmingling process of the fibres due to electric charging or non-uniform stretching when the fibre yarn was wound onto the bobbin. AS4-CF/PEEK 3K/6K powder/sheath-fibre bundles were supplied by Enichem, Italy. Before compression moulding of the composites, "flexible" unidirectional-mats were produced from the "as received" filament yarns/bundles by winding individual bundles onto an aluminium plate. Subsequently, the aligned bundle mats were welded together with a soldering iron along two transverse lines at both ends of the mats before cutting, as described in [2]. A certain number of layers of the unidirectional "prepreg" mats were packed onto each other in order to reach an estimated thickness of about 3 mm of the composite after full consolidation. The latter process was carried out in a laboratory hot press using a small steel mould with a square cavity. Once the mould reached a desired processing temperature (T_p between 360°C and 400°C) within 15 min, processing pressure was applied. Different impregnation pressures (0.5 to 3.0 MPa) and holding times (3 to 20 min) were selected to identify the impregnation mechanisms. The composite panels were cooled from the melt to room temperature at an average cooling rate of 10°C/min.

MECHANISMS OF IMPREGNATION AND CONSOLIDATION

The impregnation mechanisms were examined by reflection light microscopy in the polished cross-section of consolidated composites. The consolidation process of CF/PEEK commingled yarn is quite different from that of pre-impregnated prepreg sheets (e.g. APC-2) or powder/sheath fibre bundles as discussed hereafter, because of the difference in distribution of matrix and reinforcing fibres in the preforms. In the APC-2 CF/PEEK composites, because each individual composite prepreg sheet has been almost fully impregnated during prepreg production, consolidation of composites can be described by two regimes, i.e. bulk consolidation (where intimate ply contact is developed and spatial gaps between composite layers are eliminated to form autohesion/diffusion bonding) and resin flow (where resin percolates through fibres in each composite layer to transport the voids and to fill in matrix -depleted regions) [3], with the former as the dominate process.

However, in commingled yarn systems, the time dependent consolidation steps are quite different. First, the initially separated fibre yarns are flattened and moved towards one another when pressure is applied. With temperature increasing above T_m , the PEEK polymer fibres start to melt. At this point, the molten polymer first tends to separate out of the bundles and fill the spaces between them, which can be referred to as "unmingling". At the end of this period, the border of the dry reinforcing fibre tow can still be clearly identified. In the second step, with an increase in holding time, the applied pressure drives the molten matrix to melt-impregnate the

reinforcing fibres in the tows, thus pushing the air between them away. This process continues until the yarn is completely impregnated, and full consolidation is achieved. It can be assumed that this sequence of mechanisms dominates the whole consolidation procedure of commingled yarn based composites, although it was found that not all molten polymer leaves the fibre bundles to form a matrix pool around them in the first step.

For powder/sheath fibre bundle, it was found that the consolidation of this prepreg material can be probably described by two different procedures, i.e. compaction and impregnation. During the compaction stage, the initially separated fibre bundles were moved towards one another when pressure was applied. With temperature increasing above T_m , the sheaths around the fibre tows melt first. Coalescence between melting sheaths then occurred, so that interval spaces between fibre bundles were filled by the matrix pool, surrounding the dry fibre tow. In the second step, with increased holding time, the applied pressure drove the matrix into the reinforcing fibre tows and autohesion between the resin front and the melting powder took place, thus reducing the voids between them. This process continued until the yarn was completely impregnated and full consolidation was achieved.

IMPREGNATION MODELS

Assuming that all fibre bundles undergo impregnation simultaneously in a composite and that all of them are identical in geometry, the consolidation of the entire composite can be described by the impregnation of a representative single cell (yarn/bundle) only (Figs 1 and 2). The velocity of the matrix passing through the aligned fibres can be expressed as [4]:

$$v_r = - \frac{K_p}{\mu} \frac{dp}{dr} \quad (1)$$

where v_r is the velocity of matrix impregnation, K_p the permeability of the fibre tow estimated by the Carman-Kozeny equation [5], μ the matrix viscosity, and p the pressure. r designates the position in the flow direction. For the commingled system, as mentioned previously, the "as received" commingled status has a tendency to vanish in the initial step of the consolidation process, because the molten matrix separated out of the fibre bundles. Therefore, a parameter, $D_{com}=h_c/h_o$, should be introduced in order to indicate the degree of the commingling status at the starting point of consolidation (i.e. the bundle is partially impregnated when the processing temperature is reached). The height of the partially impregnated area is h_c . D_{com} is equal to zero for a fully unmingled yarn, whereas $D_{com}=1$ stands for a fully commingled yarn. For a desired impregnation step, $r(t)=r_f$ (Fig. 1), the void content, X_v , in the composite as a function of penetration distance is therefore [6]

$$X_v = \frac{A_m - V_m b (h_c + 2 r_f)}{A_b + A_m - V_m b (h_c + 2 r_f)} \quad (2)$$

where $V_m=1-V_f$ (volume fraction of the polymer matrix); A_b is the cross-sectional area of a fully consolidated (i.e. void free) filament yarn and $A_m=V_m \cdot A_b$. For the powder/sheath fibre bundle shown in Fig. 2, at a desired impregnation step, $r = r_f$, the remnant free space in the fibre tow can be expressed as [7]:

$$V_v = (1 - V_f - V_{mp}) \pi r_f^2 = \pi r_o^2 (1 - D_{imp}) (1 - V_f - V_{mp}) \quad (3)$$

where V_f and V_{mp} are the volume fractions of the fibres and the matrix powder between them. Hence, at a certain impregnation step, the void content, X_v , in a representative bundle is as follows:

$$X_v = \frac{V_v}{\pi r_b^2} \tag{4}$$

In this way, the consolidation quality of the entire composite can be described. Full impregnation is achieved when the molten matrix is totally transferred into the free space within the reinforcing fibre bundle. This represents a void free consolidated composite ($X_v = 0$), as shown in Figs 1c and 2c. These approaches provide relationships between the void content and the processing variables in the consolidation process of composites. In particular, these variables are (a) viscosity as a function of temperature [$\mu = \mu(T)$], (b) applied pressure, (c) holding time and (d) bundle geometry.

Fig. 1 Schematics of a representative yarn in simulating consolidation steps for partially commingled CF/PEEK composites

Fig. 2 Schematics of a representative tow in simulating consolidation steps for CF/PEEK powder/sheath fibre bundles

Fig. 3 Void content of CF/PEEK-6K powder/sheath fibre bundles as a function of holding time at two different levels of applied pressure ($T=390^{\circ}\text{C}$)

Fig. 4 Consolidation quality of CF/PEEK commingled yarn composites at different processing temperatures ($p_a = 1.5 \text{ MPa}$, $D_{\text{com}} = 75\%$)

CONSOLIDATION QUALITY AND MECHANICAL PROPERTY

Fig. 3 illustrates the void contents in the consolidated CF/PEEK-6K composites as a function of holding time at two different levels of applied pressure; the processing temperature was held constant at $T=663 \text{ K}$ ($=390^{\circ}\text{C}$), i.e. $\mu=380 \text{ Pa}\cdot\text{s}$. The symbols indicate the apparent void contents determined from the densities of the consolidated composites according to ASTM-792, and each one represents a mean value of four measurements. The solid lines indicate the predictions from the model. The results indicate the material reaches fully consolidated status when holding time exceeds 20 min at $p_a = 1 \text{ MPa}$. In Fig. 4 the void contents in commingled CF/PEEK composites

are plotted as a function of holding time at an applied pressure of 1.5 MPa; the processing temperature was kept at $T=653\text{ K}$ ($=380^\circ\text{C}$), 673 K ($=400^\circ\text{C}$, $\mu=247\text{ Pa}\cdot\text{s}$) and 693 K ($=420^\circ\text{C}$, $\mu=109\text{ Pa}\cdot\text{s}$). The prediction were made from the model at $D_{\text{com}}=75\%$. The experimental data indicate that the material reached a fully consolidated status when holding time was about 20 minutes at $p_a = 1.5\text{ MPa}$ and $T=420^\circ\text{C}$. In both cases, It can be seen that applied pressure, processing temperature (or viscosity of matrix) and holding time greatly affect the quality of consolidation. An increase in either holding time or applied pressure obviously reduced the void content in the composites, and gave better consolidated materials. From these points it can be concluded that in spite of a good distribution of the reinforcing and the polymer matrix in commingled yarn and/or powder/sheath fibre bundles (in the non-molten state), the observed unmingling step at the onset of melting of the polymer fibres and the high viscosity of the matrix at low processing temperature still obstruct fast consolidation and achieving void-free composites.

Characterisations of mechanical properties as a function of impregnation conditions were carried out by using a small transverse flexure (three point bending) testing facility. The length of the span amounted to 40 mm; the width and thickness of the specimens were about 10 mm and 2 mm, respectively. The cross-head speed was set to 2 mm/min. Transverse elastic constants and flexure strength were determined according to ASTM standard D-790. Figs. 5 and 6 illustrates effects of consolidation quality (i.e. void content) on the transverse flexure strength of CF/PEEK composites. The ultimate strength, σ_{ult} , is obviously reduced as the void content is increased. For example, for a change of the apparent void content from 23% to almost zero in the powder/sheath fibre bundles, increases in ultimate strength by, on the average, six-fold were identified. From these results, it can be stated that both transverse strength and elastic constant highly depend on the consolidation quality of the composites, which is therefore an essential factor to be considered during the manufacture of thermoplastic composites.

Fig. 5 Transverse flexure strength of powder/sheath fibre bundle CF/PEEK composites versus consolidation quality

Manufacturing of CF/PEEK composites should be based on a critical level of void content, e.g. $X_{vc}=0.5\%$. The relationships between processing temperature, applied pressure, and holding time to stay below this maximum level of void content are described in Fig. 7 for the CF/PEEK commingled yarn composites. Two processing temperatures ($T=400^\circ\text{C}$ and 415°C) were selected

for the model prediction of the relevant curves. From such a processing window, if the processing temperature is about 400°C, holding time for high quality consolidation of commingled yarn CF/PEEK with a void content of less than 0.5% will be over 60 min (indicated by the point A), at a processing pressure of 0.7 MPa. This is quite close to the results published by BASF on similar CF/PEEK commingled yarns [8], as illustrated by the solid symbols in the window (Fig. 7).

Fig.6 Transverse flexure strength of CF/PEEK commingled yarn composites versus consolidation quality

Fig. 7 Optimum processing window for manufacturing of CF/PEEK commingled yarn composites

CONCLUSIONS

The impregnation and consolidation mechanisms in CF/PEEK thermoplastic composites made from a commingled yarn and powder/sheath fibre bundle preforms have been investigated. Impregnation models have been developed to qualitatively describe consolidation processes during press. These models predict the current void content as a function of bundle geometry and processing variables (temperature, applied pressure and holding time). Good correlations with the experimental data indicate the success of these approaches. Based on a desired minimum level of void content ($X_v=0.5\%$), optimum processing windows for the manufacturing of CF/PEEK composite parts from these flexible prepreg forms are suggested. In practice, the present results would be of benefit to various manufacturing techniques of thermoplastic composites for engineering applications, e.g. for compression moulding, fast consolidation/or in-situ consolidation in filament winding and pultrusion manufacturing, etc.

A parameter has been introduced to describe the degree of commingled status which controls the consolidation of commingled yarn based composites. However, as this parameter depends on the production process of the commingled yarn, on proper "sizing" and on the subsequent procedure used to manufacture composites, the prediction of its real value is very difficult. Further work should be done to identify this essential fact.

If comparing the impregnation and consolidation mechanisms of commingled yarn based CF/PEEK composites with those in materials made out of pre-impregnated sheets (APC-2) or powder/sheath fibre bundles, longer processing times and higher applied pressure may be required to reach full consolidation. This fact indicates that further efforts should be made to investigate what is an optimum preform for manufacturing of CF/PEEK composites.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

Thanks are due to BASF-Thermoplastic Composites Division, Germany, for supplying the testing materials. Dr. L. Ye expresses appreciation to the Australian Research Council (ARC) for supporting this study by a large research grant (AB-9332172). Prof. K. Friedrich addresses his thanks to the Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (DFG) for the support of this work (DFG-FR-675-11-1). Additional thanks are due to the Fonds Der Chemischen Industrie, Frankfurt, for the help of Prof. Friedrich's research activities in 1995.

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